

**A RANDOMIZED OPEN LABELLED COMPARATIVE CLINICAL STUDY TO
EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF SHODHANA-KESARI LEPA AND SILVERON GEL
(NANO-CRYSTALLINE SILVER GEL) IN THE MANAGEMENT OF DUSHTAVRANA
W.S.R. TO CHRONIC NON-HEALING ULCERS****Dr. Kaheksha Ali^{1*}, Dr. Ashwini Hallad², Dr. Shivalingappa J. Arakeri³**¹PG Scholar, Department of Shalya Tantra, Taranath Government Ayurvedic Medical College, Ballari (Karnataka, India).²Assistant Professor Department of Shalya Tantra, Taranath Government Ayurvedic Medical College, Ballari (Karnataka, India).³Professor & HOD, Department of Shalya Tantra, Taranath Government Ayurvedic Medical College, Ballari (Karnataka, India).***Corresponding Author: Dr. Kaheksha Ali**

PG Scholar, Department of Shalya Tantra, Taranath Government Ayurvedic Medical College, Ballari (Karnataka, India).

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18085707>**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Kaheksha Ali^{1*}, Dr. Shivalingappa J. Arakeri², Dr. Ashwini Hallad³ (2026). A comparative clinical study to evaluate the efficacy of *shodhana-kesari lepa* and silveron gel (nano-crystalline silver gel) in the management of *dushtavrana* w.s.r. To chronic non-healing ulcers. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(1), 402–409. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 29/11/2025

Article Revised on 19/12/2025

Article Published on 01/01/2026

ABSTRACT

Acharya Sushruta has defined *Vrana* as condition wherein tissue undergoes destruction, which even after complete healing leaves a scar (*Vrana Vastu*) over the area which stays as long as person is alive. Wound is a break in the integrity of skin or tissue often which may be associated with disruption of structure and function. *Shalyatantra* emphasizes the significance of *Vrana*, stating that any wound affected by dosha or other factors, leading to impaired healing, is termed *Dushtavrana*. Chronic wounds are those that fail to heal over time, sometimes persisting for months or even years. The causes may include poor blood supply, venous drainage issues, nerve damage, infection, trauma, or excessive pressure. In rural areas especially, lack of proper care often worsens the condition. Effective wound healing requires removal of necrotic tissue through methods such as wet-to-dry dressings or surgical debridement. If untreated, infections can extend from superficial to deeper tissues, increasing the risk of systemic infection. Therefore, timely and appropriate management of chronic wounds is crucial.

KEYWORDS: *Vrana*, *Shodhana-kesari Lepa*, Silveron ointment.**INTRODUCTION**

Acharya Sushruta has defined *Vrana* as condition wherein tissue undergoes destruction, which even after complete healing leaves a scar (*Vrana Vastu*) over the area which stays as long as person is alive.^[1] Wound is a break in the integrity of skin or tissue often which may be associated with disruption of structure and function.^[2]

Due to apathy ahara vihara or wrongly treated by quack, *vrana* get severely vitiated and gets converted into *Dushtavrana*. *Dushtavrana* is *vrana* having feature of *Daurgandhya*, *Puyayukta*, *Utsangi*, *Chirakali*, *Dushitaraktasrava*, *Ati-gandha-varna-srava*, *Vedanayukta*, and opposite to *Shuddha vrana*.^[3] In India recent studies estimated a prevalence rate of chronic

wound at 4.5 per 1000 population, that accounts for almost 75-80% of all the vascular ulcers. Common risk factors for abnormal healing includes the presence of necrotic tissue, infection, ischemia, smoking, diabetes, malnutrition, glucocorticoid use, and radiation exposure.^[4] Modern line of treatment include wound debridement, wound dressings, nutritional supports, glycemic control, and adjuvant therapies etc. Complications of wound are infection, burning, cellulitis, itching and irritation.^[5]

The stages of wound healing have been systematically described as *Dushtavrana*, *Shuddha*, *Ruhyamana*, and *Rudha Vrana*. A wound that is contaminated by dosha or other factors is termed *Dushtavrana*, characterized by

pain, discharge, itching, abnormal shape, and delayed healing.

In modern medicine, an ulcer is defined as a discontinuity in the epithelial or mucosal surface, often due to necrosis of surface epithelium or its traumatic loss. Venous ulcers constitute around 81% of leg ulcers, with India reporting a prevalence of 4.5 cases per 1000 individuals annually. The primary cause is venous hypertension in the lower third of the leg, ankle, and dorsum of the foot, often due to varicose veins, DVT, or venous incompetence. These ulcers may be acute (painful) or chronic (painless) and are usually associated with sero-sanguineous discharge, hyperpigmentation, induration, and tenderness of the surrounding skin.

Management strategies include compression stockings, leg elevation, calf muscle exercises, antibiotics, and daily dressings with betadine or eusol. While most ulcers respond to this regimen, others may require surgical interventions like sclerotherapy, valvuloplasty, bypass surgery, or skin grafting. However, these methods are expensive, have poor prognosis, and show high recurrence rates.

Acharya Sushruta has mentioned "*Shashti Upakramas*" regarding *vrana chikitsa*, *Lepa* is considered as "*Adya-upakrama*" in *dushtavrana*.^[6] *Shodhana-kesari lepa* contain *Nimba patra*, *Tila*, *Dantimoola*, *Trivritta*, *Saindhava* and *makshika* which has *vrana shodhaka* properties that promote healing of wound. Also it's content has anti-microbial and anti-inflammatory properties.^[7]

Silver has antiseptic, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory properties and is a broad spectrum antibiotic. Nanocrystalline silver dressing is an effective antimicrobial for treating acute, chronic wounds and different types of ulcers. But on other hand it has complications like discoloration of skin and mucous membrane, itching, and irritation.^[8] Thus *Shodhana-kesari Lepa* has been taken to evaluate its efficacy in *dushtavrana* w.s.r to chronic Non-healing ulcer in comparison to Silveron Gel (Nano-crystalline Silver Gel).

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To evaluate the efficacy of *Shodhana-Kesari Lepa* in the management of *Dustavrana* w.s.r to Chronic non-healing ulcers.
- To evaluate the efficacy of Silveron Gel (Nano-Crystalline silver Gel) in the management of *Dushtavrana* w.s.r to Chronic non-healing ulcers.
- To compare the effect of *Shodhana-Kesari Lepa* & Silveron Gel (Nano-Crystalline silver Gel) in the management of *Dushtavrana* w.s.r to Chronic non-healing ulcers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study design

A comparative clinical study containing 40 patients diagnosed as *Dushtavrana* w.s.r to Chronic Non-Healing Ulcer, were included for the study and was randomly allotted into 2 groups namely Group-A (*Shodhana-Kesari Lepa*) and Group-B(*Silveron Ointment*) with 20 patients each.

B. Source of patients

A total number of 40 patients diagnosed as *Dushtavrana* of either sex was selected from OPD and IPD of Taranath Government. Ayurvedic medical college and hospital, Ballari.

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients selected between 20-70 years of age, irrespective of sex religion, occupation.
2. Specific signs and symptoms of *dusta vrana* (*durgandha yukta*, *puti puya*, *vedana*, *raga*, *kandu*, *dusta shonita shrava*, *dirghakalanubandhi*)
3. Size of ulcer within 10 cm.
4. Diabetes mellitus (under control)
5. Hypertension (under control)

Exclusion Criteria

1. If Hb% less than 10gm%
2. Malignant ulcer, Marjolin's ulcer, Burns, Nadi *vrana*.
3. Ulcer associated with chest and head injuries.
4. Ulcer associated with, HIV I & II, Hepatitis-B, Tuberculosis, Syphilis, Osteomyelitis.
5. Multiple ulcer.

INVESTIGATIONS

- CBC
- ESR
- FBS
- PPBS
- CT
- BT
- HBs Ag
- HIV 1&2
- X-ray.

MATERIALS REQUIRED FOR STUDY

Table No. 1: Showing materials require for the study.

SL NO.	Material Required	Quantity
1	Dressing Trolley	1
2	Dressing Table	1
3	Surgical Gloves 6.5	1
4	Sterile Gauze Piece	q.s.
5	Sterile Pads	q.s.
6	Sterie Artery Forcep	1
7	Normal Saline	q.s.
8	Roller Bandage	q.s.
9	Shodhana-kesari Lepa	q.s.
10	Silveron Ointment	q.s.

Table No. 2: Drugs Required For Preakation Of Shodhana-Kesari Lepa.

Sr.No.	DRUG (All in Powder form)	QUANTITY
1	Nimba patra	1part
2	Tila	1part
3	Shodhit Danti moola	1part
4	Trivrrutta	1part
5	Saindhava	1part
6	Makshika	1part

Sample Size: 40 patients of Dustavrana w.s.r to chronic non-healing ulcers were allotted into two groups namely.

No. Of Group	No. Of Patients	Drug	Duration
Group A	20	Shodhan-kesari Lepa	28 days
Group B	20	Silveron Gel	28 days

DRUG PREPARATION

- One part of coarsely powdered of each Nimba patra, tila, Danti moola and Trivrutta were mixed together. Then equal quantity of Saindhava and Makshika was added and then applied carefully on wound.
- **Danti Shodhana:** Danti root washed properly with water. It was smeared with a thin layer of paste prepared from a powder of Pippali (Piper longum Linn.) and honey then wrapped in the leaves of Kusha (Desmostachya bipinnata). The resultant was

coated with mud and Swedana (Fomented) with steam.

- Raw Drugs were collected from GMP certified Pharmacy and confirmed with the help of Department of PG studies in Dravyaguna and Lepa will be prepared under the supervision of Rasa shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana of Taranath government Ayurvedic medical college and PG centre Ballari.

METHODOLOGY

- Nature of the study was explained to the patients and written consent was taken.
- For both the groups required materials were kept ready.
- Patient was asked to sit over dressing table.
- Ulcer was cleaned with normal saline.
- Shodhana-kesari Lepa was applied in Group A and Silveron ointment was applied in Group B.
- As per mentioned in Shushruta Samhita thickness of lepa was kept as Ardra Mahisha Charmavat i.e. 4-5 mm thick and kept for 24 hrs.
- Then covered with sterile pad and dressing done with roller bandage.
- Daily dressing was done and weekly observation were noted. i.e. on 1st day 7th day 14th day 21st day and 28th day.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Assessment is based on subjective and objective parameters, assessed before and after the treatment.

Table No. 02: Showing the assessment parameters.

Subjective Parameter	Pain	P ₀ – No pain -0 P ₁ - Mild pain- 1-3 P ₂ - Moderate pain – 4-6 P ₃ - Severe pain -7-10
	Itching	No Itching -0 Mild (ocasionally)- 1 Moderate (persist all the day) – 2 Severe (Itch with scratch marks)- 3 Continuous severe (Itch disturb routine and sleep)= 4
	Gandha	No Odour - 0 Weak odour- 1 Strong odour - 2 Very strong odour - 3
Objective parameter	Parimana (Size Of Wound):.	Healed - 0 1-3cm - 1 3.1-6cm - 2 6.1-10cm- 3
	Margins-	Well-defined - 0 With advanced border of epithelium - 1 No advancing border of epithelium -2 Not well-defined -3
	Srava (Discharge)	No discharge -0 Wets 2×2cm gauze - 1 Wets 4×4cm gauze - 2 Wets>6×6cm gauze -3
	Floor (Granulation Skin)	Complete epithelization, well-defined granulation Tissue - 0 Complete epithelization, poor granulation Tissue - 1 No epithelization, granulation Tissue poorly formed - 2 No epithelization no granulation Tissue formed - 3
	Surrounding Skin	Twaka sama varna - 0 Kapota varna - 1 Shweta Rakta varna - 2 Krishna varna - 3

RESULTS**Table No. 03: Overall effect in Group A and Group B.**

Parameters	Changes	Group A	Group B
Pain	Before-After	48.89	60.98
Itching	Before-After	67.65	43.75
Foul smell	Before-After	75.00	70.00
Size	Before-After	39.53	61.11
Margins	Before-After	80.00	78.13
Floor	Before-After	80.49	77.42
Discharge	Before-After	68.41	58.06
Surrounding skin	Before-After	36.36	20.93
Overall	Before-After	62.04	58.80

Table No 05: Showing the overall comparative results of Group A and Group B

GROUP A- Application of Shodhana-Kesari

Fig no.1- Application Of Shodhana-Kesari Lepa.

Fig no.2: Application Of Shodhana-Kesari Lepa.

GROUP B- APPLICATION OF SILVERON OINTMENT

Fig no.3: Application Of Silveron Ointment.

Fig no. 4: Application Of Silveron Ointment.

DISCUSSION

In Ayurvedic classics, DuṣṭaVraṇa (chronic, non-healing ulcer with slough, discharge, foul smell, pain, and inflammation) is a major clinical challenge. Śodhana (cleansing) and Ropaṇa (healing) are the twin principles of wound management described by Ācāryas.

Tilādi Lepa, mentioned in Chakradatta (Vraṇa Cikitsā) and Rasa Taranginī, is one such formulation indicated for DuṣṭaVraṇa. It is a combination of Śodhana, Kṛmighna, and Ropaṇadravyas, designed to first cleanse and then promote healthy granulation and healing.

A. Śodhana (Debridement & Cleansing)

I. **Danti moola & Trivṛtta:** With Tikṣṇa, Uṣṇavīrya, Bhedana, Virecaka properties, they liquefy and dislodge slough, necrotic tissue, and pus. Act as natural biological debriding agents.

II. **Saindhava Lavana:** Being Sūkṣma&Vyavāyi, penetrates deep, removes slimy coverings, draws out moisture, and helps in pus drainage.

B. Kṛmighna (Antimicrobial & Anti-fetid action)

I. **Nimba Patra:** Rich in tikta-kaṣāya rasa, it is strongly kṛmighna&dāha-śamana, reducing microbial growth, foul odor, and excessive discharge.

II. **Madhu:** Acts as a natural antiseptic due to high osmolarity, low pH, and hydrogen peroxide content.

C. Śophahara (Anti-inflammatory)

I. Nimba reduces swelling and redness.

II. Saindhava helps in liquefying inflammatory exudates.

III. Madhu decreases edema and pain, providing soothing effect.

D. Ropana (Wound Healing & Granulation Promotion)

- I. **Tila:** Its snigdha and balyagunas provide nourishment to wound bed, support fibroblast proliferation, and strengthen tissue.
- II. **Madhu:** Stimulates granulation tissue, enhances epithelialization, and minimizes scar formation.
- III. **Synergistic effect:** After cleansing action of Danti–Trivṛtta–Saindhava, Tila and Madhu provide regenerative support.

E. Dāha-prasamana & Vedanāhara (Pain & Burning relief)

- I. Nimba + Madhu + Saindhava act synergistically against kṛmi (microorganisms), thus preventing secondary infection and reducing malodor.
- II. Saindhava with snigdha guna alleviates local tenderness.
 - Śodhana: Danti, Trivṛtta, and Saindhava clear slough, pus, and toxins.
 - Kṛmighna: Nimba, Madhu, and Saindhava suppress microbial load.
 - Śophahara: Inflammation and edema reduce, restoring local circulation.
 - Ropana: Tila and Madhu accelerate granulation and epithelialization.
 - Vedanāhara & Dāha-prashamana: Patient comfort is restored, wound odor reduced, and healthy healing occurs.

Tilādi Lepa is a multi-dimensional formulation in Ayurveda for Duṣṭa Vraṇa. The formulation intelligently combines Tikṣṇa-Uṣṇaśodhana dravyas (Danti, Trivṛtta, Saindhava) with Kṛmighna & Ropana dravyas (Nimba, Tila, Madhu). This ensures that the ulcer is first cleansed, microbial growth is suppressed, and then tissue healing is enhanced.

Modern research correlates these actions with antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, debriding, and wound-healing properties.

Mechanisms of Action of Nanocrystalline Silver

- Silver has been used for centuries as a topical antimicrobial agent.
- Modern formulations use nano-crystalline silver (nanosilver, silver nanoparticles, or nanocrystalline silver) to improve efficacy, sustained release, and reduce cytotoxicity compared to bulk silver salts.
- Silveron Gel / Silveron ointment is marketed in India as a nano-crystalline silver gel (e.g. composition “Nano Crystalline Silver – 20 µg” in the gel)
- Nanocrystalline silver dressings/gels are increasingly used in wound healing and management of infected ulcers, burns, and chronic wounds.

Multiple mechanisms have been proposed and supported by in vitro, in vivo, and clinical studies. The primary mechanisms can be grouped under.

1. Antimicrobial / Microbicidal Actions
2. Anti-biofilm & Disruption of Microbial Colonies
3. Anti-inflammatory / Immunomodulatory Actions
4. Modulation of Wound Healing (Pro-healing Effects / Cytotoxicity Considerations)

Antimicrobial / Microbicidal Actions

- Nano-crystalline silver exerts broad-spectrum antimicrobial effects against Gram-positive, Gram-negative bacteria, fungi, and some drug-resistant strains. Here are the specific molecular / cellular mechanisms:
 - **Release of silver ions (Ag⁺):** The nanosilver crystals slowly release Ag⁺ ions in the presence of moisture or wound exudate. These ionic species are biologically active.
 - **Membrane damage / permeability disruption:** Ag⁺ or silver nanoparticles interact with bacterial cell walls and membranes (lipid bilayers), causing structural disruption, pore formation, increased permeability, leakage of cellular contents.
 - **Interaction with proteins and enzymes:** Silver ions bind to thiol (–SH) groups, disulfide bridges, and sulfur or phosphate moieties in enzymes, membrane proteins, and transport proteins, thereby inactivating enzymatic functions, electron transport chains, respiration, metabolic pathways.
 - **Generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) / oxidative stress:** Internalized silver may generate ROS, inducing oxidative damage to proteins, lipids, DNA within microbial cells.
 - **DNA / nucleic acid damage & replication inhibition:** Silver ions can bind to nucleic acids (DNA or RNA), interfering with replication, transcription, and causing DNA strand breaks or mutations.
 - **Multi-targeted attack reducing resistance:** Because silver acts at multiple targets (membrane, enzyme systems, nucleic acids), the likelihood of bacteria developing resistance is low.
 - **Sustained release & lower toxicity:** Nanocrystalline silver is formulated to release silver ions slowly over time at effective antimicrobial concentrations, minimizing peaks that might be cytotoxic to host tissues.

Anti-biofilm & Disruption of Microbial Colonies

- One of the challenges in chronic wounds and infected ulcers is biofilm formation, which protects bacteria from host immunity and antimicrobials. Nanocrystalline silver also acts on biofilms:
 - **Penetration into biofilm matrix:** The small size and sustained release capability allow silver to penetrate biofilm exopolysaccharide matrix.
 - **Disruption of quorum sensing / biofilm signaling:** Silver may interfere with bacterial communication (quorum sensing) necessary for biofilm

maintenance. (This mechanism is less well quantified but is reported in reviews)

- Destabilization and detachment of biofilm: By killing embedded bacteria and weakening the matrix, biofilm structure is destabilized, making it easier to clear.
- Thus, silver helps reduce the microbial load not just of planktonic bacteria but embedded biofilm organisms, which is crucial in chronic wound settings.
- Reduced oxidative stress and free radical scavenging modulation: By controlling oxidative stress, silver may indirectly reduce tissue damage from free radicals in an inflamed wound.
- Induction of apoptosis in overly activated immune cells: In hyperinflammation states, silver may favor apoptosis of certain leukocytes, reducing continued tissue damage.
- By controlling excessive inflammation, silver helps shift the wound microenvironment from a destructive, nonhealing state toward a reparative state.

Modulation of Wound Healing / Pro-healing Effects

While its primary role is antimicrobial, nanocrystalline silver also influences wound healing processes.

I. Promotion of granulation tissue and re-epithelialization: Some studies show that silver-coated dressings accelerate the formation of granulation tissue and epithelial migration compared to control. For example, in clinical burn studies, nanocrystalline silver leads to faster wound closure, more healthy granulation, less slough.

II. Stimulation of fibroblasts/keratinocyte proliferation and migration: Some in vitro and in vivo data suggest silver nanoparticles can stimulate keratinocyte migration and fibroblast activity at certain (low) concentrations.

CONCLUSION

- Shodhana-kesari Lepa is having mainly Shodhana, ropana and has Anti-microbial action due to which it has shown significant effect on healing action of Vrana.
- Shodhana-kesarilepa and Silveron Ointment has shown nearly same significant result on vranashodhanaandvranaropana.
- On the basis of percentage improvement, Shodhana-kesari Lepa has showed better effect than Silveron Ointment.

REFERENCES

1. Acharya Sushruta Sushruta Samhita, with English translation of text and Dalhana Commentry with Critical notes by Vasanta Patil, Chaukhambha prakashan, oriental distributor and publisher, New Delhi, 2 nd Edition, Vol 1, Sutra Sthana, Chapter 21verse 40.
2. SRB's Manual of surgery (ED) 6th ED, Priciple and practice of woundcarebyJaypee Brothers, Medical

- Publishers(P), New Delhi 2010;11, section 1, Chapter 1, page no. 1.
3. Acharya Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita, by Ambikadutta Shastri, Varanasi, Choukhamba Sankrit Sansthan; Edition reprint 2019, Sutra sthana vol 1; Chapter 22, verse 7.
4. S. Das A concised textbook of Surgery, Kolkata, SD publications, Edition11threprint 2020, Chapter 1, page no. 9 – 10.
5. SRB's Manual of surgery (ED) 6th ED, Priciple and practice of woundcarebyJaypee Brothers, Medical Publishers(P), New Delhi 2010; 11, section 1, Chapter 1, page no. 8-9.
6. Acharya Sushruta Sushruta Samhita, with English translation of text and Dalhana Commentry with Critical notes by Vasanta Patil, Chaukhambha prakashan, oriental distributor and publisher, New Delhi, 2nd Edition, Vol 1, Sutra Sthana, Chapter 18 verse 3.
7. Dr.Chaitanya S. Badami (2022) Wound Healing Application as per Basavarjeeyam, World Journal of Pharmaceutical and medical Research, 8(7): 91- 96.
8. Joy Fong and Fiona Wood (2006) Nanocrystalline silver dressings inwound 14 management: a review, International Journal of Nanomedicine, 1(4): 441–449.
9. Rigveda, 1st Mandala, 112th Sookta, verse no. 10; 1st Mandala, 116th Sookta, verse no. 15.
10. Atharvaveda, Jala Chikitsa Sookta, 6th Kanda, 57th Chapter, verse no. 1, 2, 3. Rohini Vanaspati Sookta, 4th Kanda, 12th Chapter, verse no. 6.